

ISic3464

I.Sicily inscription 3464

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance

Victoria, found near the church of S. George (Gualtherus)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR112581

1. Iuliae Domnae Aug (ustae)
2. matris matri castrorum
3. Imp (eratoris) Caes (aris) L (uci) Septimi
4. Severi Pertinacis
5. Aug (usti) coniugi
6. municipium Gaul (itanorum)
7. p (ecunia) p (ublica) d (ecreto)
8. curant [e---]SI
9. [---]NO

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285154
EDR 112581
EDCS 22100621

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7502 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bruno, B. 2004. L'arcipelago maltese in età romana e bizantina. Attività economiche e scambi al centro del Mediterraneo. Bari. At 20-21

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